

ADVANTAGES AND ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14059654>

The digital revolution, which is manifested as a new stage of economic and technological development, has rapidly changed human life, created wide opportunities, and started a period of further tightening of the international competition field.

Nowadays, the concept of digital economy has appeared in the economic theory and practice of a few countries. This is the rapid development of digital technologies, the revolution in the information sector and the globalization of the economy distinguished by speeding up processes. The efficiency of their use has been transformed into increasing knowledge, and socio-economic relations are expanding more and more. The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits.

Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. In today's rapidly developing global economy, the digital economy is in the early stages of its development, and it will take only a few years for our era to fully transition to the digital information stage. As stated by the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "To achieve development, it is necessary and necessary for us to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension"[1].

On March 1, 1995, American programmer Nicholas Negroponte introduced the term "Digital Economy" into practice. Today, this term is used by politicians, economists, journalists, and entrepreneurs worldwide—almost everyone [2].

In the future of modern development, digital technologies such as big data processing technologies (Big Data), artificial intelligence, neurotechnologies, quantum technologies, the Internet of Things, robotics and sensorics, digital electronic platforms, cloud and mobile technologies, virtual and augmented reality technologies, crowdsourcing, blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies, ISO (International Organization for Standardization), and 3D technologies are becoming increasingly crucial [3].

Also, the digital economy is not some completely new economy that needs to be created from scratch. It is the transition of the existing economy to a new system through the creation of new technologies, platforms and business models, as well as their implementation in everyday life. The main characteristics of this system include:

- ✓ High level of automation;
- ✓ Electronic document exchange;
- ✓ Electronic integration of accounting and management systems;
- ✓ Electronic databases;
- ✓ Corporate networks.

The advantages of the digital economy are as follows:

- ✓ Reduction in payment costs (for example, resources are saved on trips to the bank and other expenses).
- ✓ More extensive and faster information about goods and services.
- ✓ Increased opportunities for goods and services to enter the global digital market.
- ✓ Rapid improvement of goods and services due to prompt feedback from consumers.
- ✓ Faster, higher quality and more convenient service [4].

As a result of reforms, openness, and development of international economic and political relations in the new Uzbekistan, opportunities for modernization of industrial sectors, technical and technological re-equipment have been created in our country. An example of this is the increasing volume of foreign trade of our country. Hundreds of expressions such as "electronic government", "electronic management", "telecommunications", "internet", "website" have become an integral part of our life.

It should be noted that some elements of the digital economy are already successfully operating in the life of our country. In particular, taking into account the mass transfer of documents and communications to digital carriers, the use of electronic signatures was allowed, and mutual cooperation with state bodies is carried out through electronic platforms [5].

The practical importance and features of the digital economy, first of all, significantly improve people's living standards, which is its main advantage.

The choice of the state to develop the digital economy opens up new directions in the field of information technologies and electronic document circulation in general. The development of "digital technologies" became possible thanks to the development of the World Wide Web and high-quality

means of communication. It should be said that currently users are actively using Telegram bots to order food, various perfumes and fashionable clothes. In addition, various online stores and electronic payment systems are also actively developing. This shows that our citizens are confident in making electronic transactions. However, to date, users have only made small transactions that do not require large costs and are not ready to significantly increase the average volume of purchases. Currently, there is a question of developing the implementation of medium and large economic transactions and financial transactions using digital technologies.

International experience shows that digital technologies are currently actively developing in the scientific community and the private sector. Therefore, it is necessary for the state to create a favorable ecosystem by supporting innovative projects and IT companies in these areas.

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